

Pilot Use Cases

- Alfresco platform
- Redmine platform
- Unified Communication platform:
 - Audio and video peer to peer and conferences
 - Presence detection, chat and message delivery
 - Web Real Time Communication (WebRTC)

Objectives

- Creation of lightweight VM images through functional descriptions
- Distributed lightweight VM image storage
- Autonomous multi-objective repository optimisation
- Elastic resource provisioning
- Information infrastructure for strategic and dynamic reasoning

Entice Environment

Domain	Innovation	Measurable Metric
VM synthesis	Automated image creation with focus on optimised image delivery operations	60% smaller, 30% faster delivery
VM analysis	Cross-Cloud image fragment identification optimised for storage size and functionality	80% less storage, 20% faster deployment
Optimisation	Pareto multi-objective (performance, cost, storage), VM repository-centric	30% faster, 25% cheaper and smaller
Performance	Elasticity metric	Percentage of QoS change higher than percentage of resource scale up/down
Semantics	Semantic interoperability in federated Clouds	25% productivity increase
SLA	Pareto SLA templates	Pareto SLA model of 25% faster Cloud federation

Use cases

Unified Communication

- WebRTC Portal: web portal for the UC.
- Kamailio: SIP server, load balancer for VOIP calls over Asterisk server.
- RTPproxy: all the flow will circulate through it.
- MySQL: data base to store registered used calls and other data.
- Asterisk: data base to store registered used calls and other data.

- Data manager
- Open source
- VM

- Project manager
- Open source
- VM

Business Plan

- UC service will use SaaS approach, implementing pay-per-use strategy.
- Flexible service, able to dynamically adapt to the needs of every client.

Product	Unified Communications service
Business model	B2B – Pay-per-use.
Final user	Company's employees/workers.
Target client	Corporate client. Municipalities and public administrations.
Sales channels	WT current sales channels • Distinctiveness: multiplatform communications, with flexibility and transference between different devices.
Main advantages for the client	• Pay-per-use: only pay for what you need, no fixed resources allocation. • Quality of Experience: dynamic resources allocation to fulfill SLAs according to demand.
SWITCH exploitation	Direct use of SWITCH results

Consortium

Contact & More Info

- Wellness Telecom Guadalupe Flores: gflores@wtelecom.es
<http://www.entice-project.eu/>

- Scientific Coordinator
Radu Prodan radu@dps.uibk.ac.at
- General Coordinator
Thomas Fahringer: tf@dps.uibk.ac.at

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 644179